

Risk Factors for Stunting In the First 1000 Days of Life

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed risk factors (ANC, pregnant women's Fe, exclusive breast milk, complementary breast milk, vitamin A, and growth monitoring) associated with stunting at the Karamat Community Health Center, Buol Regency. The sample in the research was 149 mothers of toddlers with children aged 12-24 months. The research design used an analytical survey using a cross-sectional study design. The study results showed a significant relationship between ANC examination, MP ASI, and Vitamin A administration with the incidence of stunting in the first 1000 days of life at the Karamat District Health Center. Buol with Odds Ratio (OR) values respectively 2.43, 3.42 and 7.32. Multivariate test results show that the vitamin A program consumption factor (incomplete) with OR = 7.1 has a greater tendency to experience stunting compared to the MP-ASI provision factor (inadequate) with OR = 3.2. However, the two elements, MP-ASI and vitamin A work together to determine the incidence of stunting in toddlers in this study. The conclusion from this research is that Vitamin A is The most dominant variable is related to the incidence of stunting. Therefore, it is recommended that all health workers improve services in the form of health education related to the stunting reduction acceleration program in the Buol district.

KEYWORDS: ANC, Pregnant, Exclusive breastfeeding.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
30 September 2023

Available on:
<https://ijmscr.org/>

INTRODUCTION

The problem of nutrition remains the Indonesian government's primary concern, especially regarding nutrition in toddlers. One of the issues that has become the focus is stunting, which refers to growth failure in children under five years of age (toddlers) due to chronic malnutrition and repeated infections, especially during the first 1,000 days of life (HPK). A child is considered stunted if his length or height is lower than the standard set for his age.

According to the 2018 Basic Health Research (Riskesdas), the stunting prevalence rate in Indonesia reached 30.8%. Even though it decreased compared to 2013, which was approximately 37.2%, it had a prevalence of shortness of 18.0% and very short of 19.2%. This figure is still in the large category because it is still above the optimal threshold of the World Health Organization, which is 20% and based on the results of the survey on the nutritional status of Indonesian toddlers in 2019, the prevalence of stunting in Indonesia is 27.7% and in 2021 based on the results of the Indonesian Nutritional Status Survey decreased to 24.4%.

Exclusive breastfeeding _ can reduce risk the occurrence of stunting in toddler . Achievements exclusive breastfeeding _ on Mother pregnant at the health center Karamat experience

decline from 42.4% on in 2020 to 11.5% in in 2021. If compared to with the RPJMN (Term Development Plan) target Intermediate National), achievements on not yet in 2021 achieve the targets that have been set set amounting to 45.5%. Because importance Exclusive breastfeeding is necessary done study more carry on related influencing factors achievements (Department of Health District _ Buol , 2022).

After period Exclusive breastfeeding is important for baby For get intake proper nutrition _ via MP-ASI. MP-ASI plays important role in prevent the occurrence of stunting in baby And toddler. exclusive breastfeeding need given for 6 months first , next baby must quick get MP-ASI for development And growth optimal child. MP-ASI itself given in accordance with frequency, texture, amount , cleanliness , as well as diversity type food too _ in accordance For children (Ministry Health , 2014). Nutritional status toddler Also need noticed more by parent on period gold child. According to research conducted Noverian, et al (2018) stated that there is significant relationship _ providing MP-ASI against stunting. Results initial data acquisition from Service Health District _ Boo that Stunting prevalence based on e-PPGBM report data Public health center Karamat since 2020–2022 experienced _ enhancement that is on in 2020 it was 5.9%, then on in 2021 it

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will increase to 7.9% and on in 2022 it will be 24.65%.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted at the Karamat Health Center, Buol district. This research was conducted from February to April 2023. This research method is a type of quantitative research that uses an analytic survey approach with a cross-sectional study research design. This study's population was all mothers with children aged 12-24 months in the Working Area of the Karamat Health Center, totaling 236 people. The sample in this study were mothers with toddlers aged 12-24 months

who were in the working area of the Karamat Health Center. The technique used in sampling is using the Slovin formula, so 149 respondents obtained the number of samples in this study. This analysis used the Chi-Square statistical test with a 95% confidence level ($\alpha=0.05$). Multivariate analysis used logistic regression analysis. Logistic regression To test the hypothesis on logistic regression analysis, the Wald test was used..

RESEARCH RESULTS

Table 1. The Relationship between ANC and Stunting in the First 1000 Days of Life

ANC	Stunting events				Total		P- value	OR
	Stunting		Not Stunting		N	%		
	N	%	n	%				
Incomplete	31	37.3	52	62.7	83	100	0.030	2,430
Complete	13	19.7	53	80.3	66	100		

Source: Primary data, 2023

From the statistical test results obtained p value = 0.030, because the p-value <0.05 where the degree of significance $\alpha = 0.05$, then H0 is rejected. Statistically, it can be interpreted that

there is a relationship between ANC examinations and stunting events in the first 1000 days of life.

Table 2. Correlation between Administration of Fe Tablets in Pregnant Women to Incidence of Stunting in the First 1000 Days of Life

Fe Tablets	Stunting events				Total		P- value	OR
	Stunting		Not Stunting		N	%		
	n	%	n	%				
Incomplete	28	33.3	56	66.7	84	100	0.329	1,531
Complete	16	24.6	49	75.4	65	100		

Source: Primary data, 2023

From the statistical test results obtained p value = 0.329, because the p-value > 0.05 where the degree of significance $\alpha = 0.05$, then H0 is accepted. Statistically, it can be interpreted that

there is no relationship between giving Fe tablets to pregnant women and the incidence of stunting in the first 1000 days at the Karamat Health Center, Buol District.

Table 3. The Relationship between Exclusive Breastfeeding and Stunting in the First 1,000 Days of Life

Exclusive breastfeeding	Stunting events				Total		P- value	OR
	Stunting		Not Stunting		N	%		
	n	%	n	%				
No	33	33.0	67	67.0	100	100	0.256	1,701
Yes	11	22.4	38	77.6	49	100		

Source: Primary data, 2023

The statistical test results obtained p value = 0.256 because the value of p > 0.05 where the degree of significance $\alpha = 0.05$, then H0 is accepted. Statistically, it can be interpreted that there is no relationship between exclusive breastfeeding and the

incidence of stunting in the first 1000 days.

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Table 4. The Relationship of Giving MP-ASI to Stunting in the First 1000 Days of Life

MP ASI	Stunting events				Total	P- value	OR	
	Stunting		Not Stunting					
	n	%	n	%				
Not good	39	34.8	73	65.2	112	100	0.024	3.42
Good	5	13.5	32	86.5	37	100		

Source: Primary data, 2023

The statistical test results obtained p value = 0.024 because the value of $p < 0.05$ where the degree of significance $\alpha = 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected. Statistically, it can be interpreted that there

is a relationship between the provision of MP ASI and the incidence of stunting in the first 1000 days of life

Table 5. The Relationship of Vitamin A to Stunting in the First 1000 Days of Life

Vitamin A	Stunting events				Total	P- value	OR	
	Stunting		Not Stunting					
	n	%	n	%				
It is not following	25	61.0	16	39.0	41	100	0,000	7.32
In accordance	19	17.6	89	82.4	108	100		

Source: Primary data, 2023

The statistical test results obtained p value = 0.000 because the p-value < 0.05 where the degree of significance $\alpha = 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected. Statistically, it can be interpreted that there is a

relationship between the administration of vitamin A and the incidence of stunting in the first 1000 days of life.

Table 6. The Relationship between Growth Monitoring and Stunting in the First 1,000 Days of Life

Growth Monitoring	Stunting events				Total	P- value	OR	
	Stunting		Not Stunting					
	n	%	n	%				
Not a routine	38	31.4	83	68.6	121	100	0.416	1,679
Routine	6	21.4	22	78.6	28	100		

Source: Primary data, 2023

From the statistical test results, it was obtained that p-value = 0.416 because the p-value > 0.05 where the degree of significance $\alpha = 0.05$, then H_0 is accepted. Statistically, there is no relationship between growth monitoring and the incidence of stunting in the first 1000 days at the Karamat Health Center, Buol District.

The results of the analysis using the chi-square test showed that of the six independent variables, 3 (three) variables were

bivariate and significantly related to the incidence of stunting, namely ANC, provision of MP-ASI, and consumption of Vitamin A supplement programs (P value < 0.05). The Odds Ratio (OR) values, respectively, are 2.43, 3.42, and 7.32. Variables that qualify for multivariate analysis are those with a $p < 0.05$. Only three of the six independent variables meet the requirements to continue the multivariate test: ANC, MP-ASI, and Vitamin A.

Table 7. Analysis of the relationship between ANC examination, provision of MP-ASI and Vitamin A supplements to the incidence of stunting in the first 1000 days of life

	Variable	B	S.E	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp (B)
Step 1	ANC	,432	,467	,856	1	,355	1,540
	MP-ASI	1,266	,570	4,943	1	,026	3,548
	vitamin A	1,767	,459	14,814	1	,000	5,853
	Constant	-2,738	,626	19,136	1	,000	,065
Step 2	MP-ASI	1,155	,557	4,295	1	,038	3,175
	vitamin A	1,958	,416	22,106	1	,000	7,085
	Constant	-2,460	,542	20,589	1	,000	,085

Source: Primary data

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Table 7 shows that in the last stage, namely Step 2, the result was that the most dominant factor influencing the incidence of stunting was the administration of vitamin A with a p-value = 0.000 < 0.05, the administration of vitamin A was the factor that had the most significant influence on the incidence of stunting, with the highest Wald statistical value, namely 22.106.

Based on the results of the multivariate analysis, the riskiest factor influencing stunting was vitamin A with a p-value = 0.000 < 0.05, OR 7.085, and with the highest Wald statistical value, namely 22.106 (Jusuf et al., 2022). The number of Posyandu visits in the working area of the Karamat Health Center is still low, only around 40% - 50%; administration of high doses of Vitamin A is one of the government programs carried out twice a year every February and August. The low number of visits at Posyandu greatly affected the coverage of vitamin A administration.

These results align with Nabilla's research (2018), which stated that there was a significant relationship between the average intake of vitamin A and p = 0.006. Vitamin A has a role in visual function, cell epithelialization, growth and development, and reduced appetite (Almatsier, 2009). Provision of vitamin A is a government program in health centers, especially posyandu, which is given twice a year in February and August, together with measles immunization. Vitamin A is intended for children aged 6-59 months (Ministry of Health, 2016).

The main level of adequacy of vitamin A is through food intake, which can be obtained through fruits and vegetables full of vitamins. Usually, fruits and vegetables that are orange and red contain lots of vitamin A. You can also get them through side dishes such as fish, eggs, and shrimp. Vitamin A supplementation, regularly scheduled for February and then continued in August, is a preventive measure to prevent vitamin A deficiency and can reduce the incidence of measles and diarrhea. With a routine schedule for giving vitamin A to toddlers, it is hoped that children will become healthy and strong so that their immunity will increase, and growth and development will be optimal (PUSDATIN et al. of Health, 2016).

CONCLUSION

There are variables most at risk with stunting in the first 1000 days of life at the Karamat Health Center, Kab. Buol, i.e., Provision of vitamin A with a p-value = 0.000 < 0.05, OR value of 7.085, and the highest Wald statistical value, namely 22.106

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